

D7.3

Toolkit for IPTP and IPSP network

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable outlines the key guidelines and frameworks for managing the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) Registry and Forum – two virtual platforms supporting the Diamond Open Access (OA) community in Europe. The Registry focuses on Institutional Service and Technology Providers, while the Forum connects individual community members. The document covers three main areas: Community, Communication, and Governance. It includes strategies for user onboarding, community engagement and moderation, messaging and narrative frameworks, and alignment with EDCH’s broader governance. These measures aim to foster participation, streamline communication, and support the long-term growth of the EDCH community.</p>

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List of Acronyms

CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DAU/MAU	Daily Active Users/Monthly Active Users
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
Diamond OA	Diamond Open Access
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging
ERA	European Research Area
ERAC	European Research Area and Innovation Committee
FSDs	Funders, Sponsors, and Donors
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Tools & Technology Provider
NNC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access

PID	Persistent Identifier
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
TF	Task Force
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable gives an outline of those guidelines and frameworks designed to manage the [European Diamond Capacity Hub \(EDCH\)](#)¹ service [Registry & Forum](#)². The EDCH Registry & Forum serve as virtual spaces for the European Diamond Open Access (OA) community. While the Registry targets organisations, i.e. Institutional Publishing Service Providers and Institutional Publishing Tools & Technology Providers, the Forum is a space for individuals engaged in the European Diamond OA community to connect, share experiences and knowledge. The measures, tools and guidelines drafted below aim to engage and onboard users of the EDCH Registry & Forum, facilitate community management and communication activities.

After an introductory section, the deliverable covers three areas that are mirrored in the overall structure of the deliverable: 1) Community (see chapter 3), 2) Communication (see chapter 4), and 3) Governance (see chapter 5).

The chapter “Community” contains subsections on both, “Community Management” (see 3.1) and “Community Engagement” (see 3.2). The subchapter 3.1 “Community Management” lays out a translation workflow for translating resources of the EDCH, presents an EDCH Presentation Kit that has been created to facilitate onboarding users, and explains the initial structure of the Forum and the Forum’s concept of moderation. The subsequent subchapter 3.2 “Community Engagement” presents user and moderation guidelines created for the Forum, the EDCH [EDIB policy](#) and the criteria for inclusion in the Registry. Additionally, the subchapter explains how community engagement will be tracked through metrics such as number of active users, new registrations, topics created, replies posted, total reading time, and the Daily Active Users/Monthly Active Users (DAU/MAU) ratio.

Chapter 4 “Communication” introduces a “Key Messaging Framework” (see chapter 4.1) for the EDCH Registry and Forum that collects key messages around the functionalities and opportunities the EDCH Registry & Forum offer, connects them to target audiences and EDCH services other than the EDCH Registry & Forum they may reference.

The following subchapter 4.2 “Narrative Framework for the EDCH Registry & Forum” serves as a guideline on how to describe the EDCH Registry & the Forum, explain their respective purpose and their connection to each other.

Lastly, chapter 5 “Governance” outlines the connection between the EDCH Registry & Forum and the overall EDCH governance.

¹ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *Home*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/>.

² European Diamond Capacity Hub. *EDCH Registry and Forum*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://registry.diamas.org/>.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Development & Objective

This deliverable serves as a toolkit for developing and managing the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) network of Institutional Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Tools & Technology Providers (IPTPs). The EDCH is a collective that provides services for Diamond Open Access (OA) Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools & Technology Providers. The network of IPSPs and IPTPs is a service of the EDCH that is labelled “Registry & Forum”, virtual spaces dedicated to fostering collaboration and networking among Diamond OA Community Members. The contents of this toolkit have been prepared by members of the [DIAMAS³](#) (Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication) and [CRAFT-OA⁴](#) (Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access) projects, as well as the coordination team of the [EDCH⁵](#). The objective of this deliverable is to prepare a document that provides the team operating the network of IPSPs and IPTPs with sufficient guidance and tools to guarantee the day-to-day management of the network. The operating team consists of members of the [EDCH coordination team⁶](#) and the [EDCH Task Forces⁷](#). Simultaneously, this deliverable aims to ensure that the sustainability of the network is supported by outlining engagement measures and communication activities that help the network grow beyond its initial user base provided by the projects. This deliverable complements the DIAMAS deliverable 4.5 “IPSPs registry” that is due in June 2025. Deliverable 4.5 presents the design, implementation, and strategic role of the EDCH’s Registry and Forum, outlining the methodology used.

This deliverable provides a toolkit for what will effectively consist of the [EDCH Registry & Forum⁸](#), launched in April 2025. Some of the contents have been created within the context of the engagement, dissemination and communication activities of both DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA. Due to their individual focus on complementary aspects of Diamond OA, DIAMAS is responsible for the parts covering IPSP participation in the EDCH Forum & Registry and CRAFT-OA for those parts concerned with the participation of IPTPs. Those contents already in existence have been reviewed and refined in order to be added to this toolkit as a tool tailored to the needs of the EDCH Registry & Forum. Additionally, this toolkit contains parts that have been created

³ DIAMAS Project: *Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamasproject.eu/>.

⁴ CRAFT-OA. *Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://www.craft-oa.eu>.

⁵ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *Homepage*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/>.

⁶ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *The EDCH Coordination Team*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/edch-coordination-team>.

⁷ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *Task Forces*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/task-forces>.

⁸ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *EDCH Registry and Forum*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://registry.diamas.org/>.

explicitly for the onboarding of IPSPs and IPTPs in collaboration with the EDCH coordination team.

The tools provided through this deliverable are categorised in the following two sections: 1) “Community”, containing the subsections “Community Management” and “Community Engagement”, 2) Communication, including key messages, a narrative framing of the EDCH Registry & Forum and communication material. Additionally, a third section covering the governance of the EDCH Registry & Forum provides the organisational framework for the management of the network, while simultaneously explaining the connection to the overall [governance of the EDCH](#)⁹.

2.2 Definitions for IPSP and IPTP:

In a first step, concise definitions for both IPSPs and IPTPs have been created. These definitions build the basis for the registration process in the registry, essentially allowing providers to self-identify. Applications for the registry undergo a review that is further described in 3.2 “Criteria for Inclusion in the Registry”. The definitions agreed upon through the cross-project working group read as follows:

Definition IPTP (Institutional Publishing Tools & Technology Provider): Any entity that provides tools and/or technologies such as standards, code, hardware and software that enable any user and service provider to perform specific tasks or operations to achieve their objectives. Such tools and technologies include, but are not limited to, publishing software, format converters, Extensible Markup Language (XML) and content structuration standards, peer review management systems, editing tools, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), data exchange protocols, etc.

Definition IPSP (Institutional Publishing Service Provider): Any entity that provides services and/or infrastructure to authors and publishers for scholarly publishing. These services may be provided by the institutional publisher itself (in which case the institutional publisher is also the IPSP) or by other entities inside or outside the institution. Such activities include, but are not limited to: (a) editorial activities (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, etc.); (b) operational activities (production activities like copy editing, proofreading, type-setting, creating metadata), IT activities, communication activities (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.), as well as administrative and financial activities (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.).

⁹ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *Governance*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/governance>.

3 COMMUNITY

The maintenance and sustainability of the EDCH Registry & Forum are bound to its role to manage and foster a thriving, engaged IPSP/IPTP community. Necessarily, this will involve encouraging active daily participation and managing this activity. Non-registered users and registered users alike have reading access; registered users of the Forum can furthermore actively participate in the discussions taking place in the Forum.

3.1 Engagement

In terms of the community network for IPSPs and IPTPs, that is the EDCH Registry & Forum ‘engagement’ refers to the engagement of two specific target audiences: Organisations that are an IPTP and/or IPSP and individuals who represent those organisations. While organisations will mainly be incentivised to join the Registry, the Forum will bring together individuals from registered organisations to foster lively community discussions and best practices exchange. The Registry and the Forum are therefore interconnected.

EDCH Presentation Kit

To explain the connection between the Registry and the Forum and bring forward the advantages of joining, a comprehensive [EDCH Presentation Kit](#)¹⁰ has been created. It is designed to introduce IPSPs and IPTPs to the EDCH Registry & Forum and its services. This kit offers a clear, step-by-step guide on joining the network, accessing its services, and engaging with other stakeholders. It differentiates between the onboarding processes for organisations and individuals, ensuring both types of members can contribute effectively. Additionally, it is designed to help IPSPs/IPTPs understand how they can benefit from and contribute to the EDCH ecosystem.

¹⁰ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *EDCH step-by-step kit* [PDF]. Retrieved June 17, 2025, https://diamas.org/sites/default/files/2025-06/EDCH_Step%20by%20step%20kit.pdf.

Figure 1: EDCH Presentation Kit

Translation Workflow

A key responsibility of the Diamond OA community assembled through the EDCH will be making EDCH resources accessible in multiple languages. To support this effort that will be spearheaded by the language communities themselves, a translation workflow has been developed. The aim is to ensure that materials are available in different languages, reflecting the network's diversity, fostering a more inclusive and global community of IPTPs and IPSPs. Additionally, the Forum will provide topics for discussions in multiple languages that will be moderated by members of the respective language communities.

Step	Name of step	Description
1	Identify the translation coordinator	The translation coordinator is an individual assigned to oversee, coordinate and finally deliver the translation of EDCH content. There will be at least one translation coordinator per language. They will be supported through coordination and collaboration within the framework of the EDCH Community Task Force . ¹¹
2	Content identification	The content to be translated has to be identified by the EDCH Community Task Force and, if possible, the language community targeted.

¹¹ European Diamond Capacity Hub (DIAMAS). *Task Forces*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/task-forces>.

3	Community coordination	The translation coordinator will encourage and identify members of their language community to participate in the translation effort, e.g. by raising the visibility of the most active translators through active mentions. The coordinator's responsibility is to coordinate the translation by members of the respective linguistic community.
4	Prioritise identified content	Depending on the translation capacity of the linguistic community, the translation coordinator may incentivise the team translating to prioritise the content identified.
5	Translation phase	The team working on the translation may use tools such as DeepL and the translation platform Mondaecus ¹² to translate, depending on their capacity, the linguistic communities' respective needs and conditions.
6	Review and quality check	The translation created has to be reviewed, checking it for idiomatic accuracy, congruence with the original material and overall comprehensibility. The review is to be coordinated and approved by the translation coordinator.
7	Approval by translation coordinator	The reviewed and quality-checked translation has to be approved by the translation coordinator.
8	Submission to EDCH community manager	The approved translation will be submitted to the EDCH community manager.

Table 1: Translation Workflow

EDCH Forum Moderation & Initial EDCH Forum Structure

As a measure to manage the Forum, moderators were initially selected from within the two project consortia to ensure familiarity with the EDCH services that derive from the outputs of DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA. Their role goes beyond merely overseeing the

¹² MONDAECUS is a free-software platform, an innovative online platform developed by the University of Coimbra. MONDAECUS supports machine translation, collaborative work and simultaneous input from multiple translators. The platform is available under <https://www.mondaecus.com/>

discussions – they are specifically instructed to be proactive and actively engage in early discussions, helping to foster a welcoming atmosphere and draw participants into meaningful dialogue. To further support engagement, the EDCH Forum has initially been organised according to seven distinct dimensions of the [Diamond Open Access Standard \(DOAS\)](#)¹³:

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission and governance
3. Open Science
4. Editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity
5. Technical service efficiency
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB), multilingualism and gender equity.

Complementing these specified categories are broader ones, introduced to enhance interaction among users:

8. General: news, events, newcomer introductions, and general discussions
9. Feedback: discussion about the Forum, its organisation, how it works, and how it can be improved.

While these categories provide the initial framework, the Forum is designed to be flexible and adaptable. As participation grows, the structure can be extended or modified based on evolving needs. Recently, additional private categories have been introduced that are accessible only to designated members of specific working groups:

- Registry: A dedicated space for the Registry moderation team to review submissions and address related issues.
- Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH): Used by the DDH team to coordinate on verification issues and assess journals' compliance.
- National Capacity Centres (NNC): Supports the establishment and strategic development of a network of NNCs.

3.2 Community Management

Guidelines

To manage the community brought together in the EDCH Forum, several guidelines have been created:

¹³ Diamond Open Access Standard. (n.d.). *Diamond Open Access Standard* [Brochure]. Zenodo. Retrieved June 17, 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14892096.

- [EDCH Forum guidelines](#)¹⁴, a guide for polite and respectful behaviour targeting users of the EDCH Forum that is compliant with the values of the EDCH. Additionally, specific guidelines for EDCH Forum moderators have been created. They take into account the specific contribution of moderators to the maintenance and support of the Forum and provide the basis for a consistent management of the Forum. The guidelines for Forum moderators are available to Forum moderators.
- [An EDIB policy](#)¹⁵, helping to create and maintain a safe and inclusive research culture and a working environment that enables everyone to contribute to and benefit from advancements in arts, humanities and sciences.

Criteria for Inclusion in the Registry

Additionally, three criteria for the inclusion of organisations have been created to ensure compliance with the profile of the EDCH Registry as a free resource that allows Publishers, Service Providers and Tools and Technology Providers involved in Diamond OA publishing to register and publish their profile in a way that highlights their fields of expertise and operational capacities.

These criteria are designed to cater to the core principles of Diamond OA, e.g. community ownership:

1. Be active in the Diamond OA publishing ecosystem
2. Commit to community ownership
3. Be a public legal entity (i.e. have an identified legal status)
4. Be part of the European landscape: Must be either located in – or have a parent organisation located in – a country that is part of the [European Research Area](#)¹⁶ (ERA) or an observer to the [European Research Area and Innovation Committee](#)¹⁷ (ERAC).

These criteria are laid out in detail on the [EDCH Registry webpage](#)¹⁸.

Metrics

The metrics of the EDCH Forum focus on tracking community engagement and activity, including the number of active users, new registrations, topics created, replies

¹⁴ The EDCH Community. (2025, March 28). *Our forum guidelines*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, from <https://forum.diamas.org/t/our-forum-guidelines/81>.

¹⁵ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *EDIB Policy*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diamas.org/edib-policy>.

¹⁶ European Commission. *European Research Area Platform*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/>.

¹⁷ Council of the European Union. (n.d.). *European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC)*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/council-eu/preparatory-bodies/european-research-area-and-innovation-committee-erac/>.

¹⁸ European Diamond Capacity Hub. *Register an organisation*. EDCH Registry. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://registry.diamas.org/register>.

posted, total reading time, and the Daily Active Users/Monthly Active Users (DAU/MAU) ratio, which indicates how often users return and engage with the Forum. Usage metrics are a built-in functionality of Discourse, the software used to create the EDCH Forum. This data provides an overview of the vitality of discussions and member participation.

As of June 13th, 2025, the Forum has reached 113 members. Between March 13th and June 13th, 2025, the DAU/MAU ratio stands at 21%, which is a positive signal, surpassing the recommended benchmark of 20%. During the same period, 115 posts have been published, and we continue to observe a steady flow of new registrations.

Site traffic

Figure 2: Forum: Site traffic (March 13th-June 13th, 2025)

For the Registry, analytics will be handled through Matomo, an open-source web analytics platform that respects user privacy on a server hosted in the Schengen area to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Metrics will include visits, page views, user interactions, and navigation paths. This information will help us understand how the Registry is accessed and used, enabling us to improve its usability and impact over time.

Registry: Country of Registration (as of June 13th, 2025)

Country	Number of registrations
Croatia	1

Czechia	1
Denmark	1
Egypt	1 (French organisation)
France	13
Germany	11
Greece	1
Ireland	1
Italy	4
Lithuania	4
Netherlands	3
North Macedonia	1
Norway	1
Poland	1
Serbia	20
Slovenia	1
Spain	4
Switzerland	2
Tunisia	2
United Kingdom	15
TOTAL	88

Table 2: EDCH Registry: Country allocation

4 COMMUNICATION

Based on the engagement activity already conducted in the DIAMAS project, the Key Messaging Framework for the EDCH Registry & Forum is tailored to specifically target users of the EDCH Registry & Forum and guide them to the other services of the EDCH to help them make full use of the ecosystem of resources.

Complementarily, the Narrative Framework laid out in chapter 4.2 guides the general gist of all communication around the EDCH Registry & Forum and the service's relation to the other services of the EDCH.

4.1 Key Messaging Framework

The Key Messaging Framework for the EDCH Registry & Forum collects key messages to be communicated, connects them to specific target audiences, the EDCH-related service other than the EDCH Registry & Forum they may point to, and, lastly, lists the preferred channels of communication that are deemed to be the most impactful.

EDCH services that the EDCH Registry & Forum may point to are:

- **DOAS and its self-assessment tools**

The DOAS is an instrument that helps foster quality assurance in Diamond OA publishing. DOAS includes both a practical guide and benchmarking resources for checking quality and sustainability. The DOAS and self-assessment tools allow Diamond OA Publishers and Providers to assess their compliance with the seven quality components of DOAS, as well as their financial sustainability.

- **Resources & Guidelines**

This is a set of resources that support publishers moving towards Diamond OA. They include concise high-level introductions to Diamond OA and the DOAS as well as guidelines and good practices for journal publishing. Additionally, this component of the EDCH offers detailed instructions and practical guidance to assist Diamond OA publishers in meeting the standards outlined in the DOAS.

- **Training Platform**

The Training Platform is dedicated to helping Diamond Publishing Service and Diamond Tools & Technology Providers enhance their skills and build capacity by offering skill-building training modules and curricula in various areas, including the seven components of the DOAS.

- **Diamond Discovery Hub**

The DDH aims to provide an authoritative list of Diamond OA journals in Europe, helping these journals increase their visibility in the academic community and beyond. Diamond OA journals included in the DDH must fulfil the [six operational criteria for Diamond Open Access](#)¹⁹. They can subsequently work towards meeting the DOAS quality criteria.

- **Publishing Tools**

Publishing Tools refers to a set of software tools, add-ons and other technical developments that serve to improve technical efficiency at the level of publishing workflows and platforms. The publishing tools will also furnish the necessary components to ensure seamless interoperability between various publishing software solutions.

Message	Target Audience(s)	EDCH services related (prioritised)
We aim to build a community of Diamond OA publishers allowing greater collaboration, learning, and knowledge sharing - strength in numbers!	IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 Registry
Join a vibrant network and raise the profile of your Diamond OA publishing activities	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Registry 2 Forum
Stay up-to-date with everything Diamond OA in the ERA through the network	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 Registry
Find guidance, tools & technologies tailored for the needs of quality Diamond OA publishing	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 DOAS 3 Resources & Guidelines 4 Publishing Tools 5 Training Platform
Get recognition for your role in strengthening Diamond OA publishing	IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Registry
Build your collaboration network by identifying partners, their services, and	individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 Registry

¹⁹ CRAFT-OA. *Operational Diamond OA criteria for journals*. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://www.craft-oa.eu/operational-diamond-oa-criteria-for-journals/>.

competencies in the comprehensive EDCH Registry & Forum		
Share your experiences and good practices with peers	Individuals	1 Forum
Ask your questions, get help, solve your issues	Individuals	1 Forum
Join the community of practice: Shape a virtual space to interact and exchange knowledge and support its development into an engaged and responsive community of practice	Individuals	1 Forum
Design & support a comprehensive Diamond OA policy/strategy (point to recommendations)	Institutional leaders, Policymakers, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors (FSD)	1 Forum 3 Resources & Guidelines
Tap into the expertise available in the community	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum
Increase your visibility by registering and presenting your organisation's profile, expertise, and operational capabilities	IPSP/IPTPs	2 Registry
Build your collaboration network by connecting with like-minded organisations	IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 Registry
Share your experiences, new developments and good practices with peers and get recognition for your role in strengthening Diamond OA publishing	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum
Stay informed with up-to-date insights on the Diamond OA landscape and discover	individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum

technologies tailored to your needs		
Raise your profile and gain recognition for your role in shaping the future of OA publishing	IPSPs/IPTPs, FSDs,	1 Forum 2 Registry
Find collaborators and partners, from institutional publishers to infrastructure providers	Individuals, IPSPs/IPTPs	1 Forum 2 Registry
Strengthen your OA strategy by learning from peers and established models	IPSPs/IPTPs, FSDs, national governments	1 Forum 3 Resources & Guidelines

Table 3: Key Messaging Framework

4.2 Narrative Framework for the EDCH Registry & Forum

The narrative framework for the EDCH Registry & Forum serves as a guideline on how to describe the EDCH Registry & the Forum, their respective purpose and their connection to each other.

EDCH Registry

Description	The EDCH Registry is a list of institutions that are registered with the EDCH and fulfil the selection criteria explained above. It serves as an entry point to the EDCH services for IPSPs and IPTPs.
Purpose	The EDCH Registry is a space for organisations to highlight their services, increase their overall visibility and connect to a network of Service, Technology & Tools providers dedicated to Diamond OA.
Workflow joining the EDCH registry	To join the EDCH Registry, an organisation must be actively involved in the Diamond OA ecosystem (as an IPSP or IPTP), demonstrating a clear commitment to community ownership and operating as a recognised legal entity. The registration process begins with creating an account using an institutional email, followed by completing the organisation's profile with key details such as services offered and main contacts. Once submitted, the Registry admin team (EDCH Executive Manager and Community

	Task Force (TF) Leads) reviews the information, requests any necessary updates, and, upon approval, publishes the organisation’s profile. Existing profiles can be updated by requesting management rights and submitting revised information for validation.
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Table 4: Narrative Framework EDCH Registry

EDCH Forum

Description	The EDCH Forum is designed as a space for people—a communicative and inclusive environment where members of the Diamond OA community can interact with each other. It is open to individuals across disciplines involved with Diamond OA. It is open for everyone to read, and users can register when affiliated with a registered IPSP or IPTP. If their organisation is not registered, users may register by explaining their involvement in the European Diamond OA publishing landscape.
Purpose	The Forum aims to assemble a “community of communities”, encouraging open dialogue, knowledge exchange, project collaboration, and community support. Registered users of the EDCH Forum can initiate discussions, share experiences, and actively engage with the Diamond OA community.
Workflow joining the EDCH Forum	Members of registered organisations, as well as individuals actively engaged in the European Diamond OA landscape, are welcome to join the forum to connect with the community, exchange knowledge, and collaborate on shared challenges. To participate, users must create an account, indicating their organisation—if it is listed in the EDCH Registry—or, if not, providing a brief explanation of their involvement in Diamond OA publishing to support their request for access.

Table 5: Narrative Framework EDCH Forum

Additionally, multimedia communication and dissemination material has been created to guide users through the registration process and facilitate a smooth introduction to the available services:

- [EDCH Flyer](#)²⁰

²⁰ European Diamond Capacity Hub. (2025). *Brochure EDCH* [PDF]. Retrieved June 17, 2025, <https://diameter.org/sites/default/files/Communication%20Kit/Brochure%20EDCH%20digital.pdf>.

Figure 3: EDCH Flyer front

Figure 4: EDCH Flyer back

- Two instructional videos illustrating how to join the registry
 - [EDCH Registry - Register an organisation](#)²¹
 - [EDCH Registry - Update an organisation profile](#)²²

²¹ OPERAS Research Infrastructure. (2025, June 17). EDCH Registry - Register an organisation [Video]. YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UaL5yGiZA6Q>.

²² OPERAS Research Infrastructure. (2025, June 17). EDCH Registry - Update an organisation profile [Video]. YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9NvX9-7jqQY>.

- [Poster presenting the EDCH services](#)²³

Figure 5: A poster presenting the EDCH services

²³ Kuchma, I., Paulhac, M., Stokanovski, J., & Ševkušić, M. (2025). *European Diamond Capacity Hub: Supporting Integrity and Equity in Diamond Open Access Publishing* [Poster]. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15526130](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526130).

5 GOVERNANCE

The governance scheme feeds directly from the EDCH governance scheme and adds elements that are specific to the EDCH Forum and Registry.

For the EDCH, there are three levels of governance: the EDCH Assembly, the Steering Committee and the Executive Committee.

The EDCH Assembly consists of Community Members: representatives of Diamond Capacity Centers, Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools & Technology Providers that join the EDCH. Community Members can participate in various Task Forces. The purpose of the EDCH Assembly is to advise the EDCH **Steering Committee**. The **Steering Committee** is composed of public and not-for-profit organisations (e.g. charities, foundations, associations, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)) that financially contribute to the EDCH, and the **Executive Committee** oversees its daily operations. The purpose of the Steering Committee is to guide the development of the EDCH. National and international organisations involved in various aspects of Diamond OA publishing are part of this committee and contribute in kind by leading key EDCH Task Forces and Services. The Steering Committee consists of [supporting members](#) and appoints the Executive Committee.

Since the EDCH Assembly consists of **Community Members**, governance of the IPTP/IPSP Network represents the community. To become a part of the Assembly, IPSPs or IPTPs must register within the Registry and follow the rules of the Registry. The Forum becomes a place for interaction and community-building.

Each member organisation appoints or delegates among themselves a contact person, i.e. representative who will represent the organisation in the EDCH Assembly.

6 CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

This toolkit will serve as a living framework to guide the community engagement of the EDCH Registry & Forum. With this service having gone online in May 2025, the tools and measures outlined here will be put into practice. In collaboration with community members, they will be continuously adapted, and, whenever needed, expanded, to serve the needs of the European Diamond OA community.

Additionally, several measures to improve the functionality, transparency and overall reach are already envisioned:

- The metrics tracked to monitor user engagement in the EDCH Registry & Forum will be reviewed and evaluated at regular intervals.
- Close collaboration with NCCs for Diamond OA is currently in preparation. This collaboration will serve as a gateway to national and regional communities. With the activities and the community engagement of the NCCs to be coordinated through the Forum, this collaboration helps enhance the sustainability of the EDCH Registry & Forum.
- To further enhance the translation workflow, automatic translation tools will be tested for implementation in the workflow.

Together, these evolving tools, partnerships, and frameworks will ensure that the EDCH Registry & Forum becomes a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable resource for the European Diamond OA community.

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